

Finite element implementation of finite strain constitutive models formulated in the logarithmic strain space

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1. Introduction

In many real-world applications, solids undergo severe deformation. In such situations, the continuum mechanics description must extend beyond the infinitesimal strain setting and employ the finite strain theory. It usually requires reformulation of the constitutive model, which poses both theoretical and computational challenges, especially when multiplicative decomposition of strain gradient is applied, e.g., due to inelastic deformation mechanisms. In their seminal papers [2, 3], Miehe and coworkers developed an alternative approach that benefits from constitutive models developed for small deformations and seamlessly integrates them into the generalized logarithmic strain space. The primary concern then shifts from the development of constitutive theories to the adoption of geometric transformations that convert the outputs of the constitutive law from this space into objects appropriate for further computational treatment, e.g., with finite element methods (FEM).

This paper exemplifies the procedure and its numerical implementation, including the incorporation into FEM, on a three-dimensional linear elasticity model. The procedure encompasses both the pre-processing phase, in which the logarithmic strain measure is computed from displacements, the resolution of the constitutive model, and the post-processing phase, in which the fundamental quantities (stress tensor, tangent modulus) must be consistently transformed to comply with the particular FEM formulation. Our algorithmic realization of the FEM employing Newton's iterative method relies on the methodology described in [1].

2. Constitutive Models in the Logarithmic Strain Space

Many FEM software suites enable users to implement specific constitutive behaviours of materials through an independent routine that communicates with the FEM core code through inputs and outputs. A schematic workflow of the constitutive routine takes the form

$$\{\mathbf{E}, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{P}\} \rightarrow \text{Constitutive Model} \rightarrow \{\mathbf{T}, \mathbb{D}, \tilde{\mathcal{F}}\}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{E} denotes the symmetric strain tensor, \mathbf{T} is the corresponding work-conjugate stress tensor, \mathbb{D} is the tangent (constitutive) modulus, \mathcal{F} and $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$ denote a specific set of internal variables at the input and their updated values at the output, respectively, and \mathcal{P} is a set of auxiliary parameters. Recall that given a displacement U , the corresponding deformation gradient is set as $\mathbf{F} = \nabla U + \mathbf{I}$ and the right Cauchy-Green tensor as $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^\top \mathbf{F}$. All the variables are considered as fields over a domain Ω . In classical linear elasticity, the constitutive law, $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbb{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, returns the Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ as the output, \mathbf{T} , based on the infinitesimal strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ entering as \mathbf{E} ; $\mathbb{D} = \mathbb{C}$ is the fourth-order stiffness tensor and \mathcal{F} , $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$ and \mathcal{P} are empty sets.

Algorithm 1: Condensed computational workflow

1. FEM assemblies (based on [1]):
 - i) discretization of the computational domain Ω into elements,
 - ii) computing the values of the local basis functions and their derivatives at the Gauss (integration) points, element volumes, etc.
2. Assembly of the deformation-displacement matrix B and the global elastic stiffness matrix K_e .
3. FOR-loop over time steps:
 - i) setting the boundary conditions and the initial displacements U_t ,
 - ii) WHILE-loop of Newton's method for solving a nonlinear system:
 - A) Preprocessing:
 - a) determining F from U and computing $C = F^\top F$,
 - b) computing the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of C and then E via (2),
 - B) Resolution of the constitutive problem (1),
 - C) Postprocessing:
 - a) computing the transformation tensors \mathbb{P} and \mathbb{L} from (3),
 - b) computing P and \mathbb{M} using (4) (and additionally S , σ via (5)),
 - D) assembly of the global tangent matrix K_t utilizing \mathbb{M} ,
 - E) computing new displacements U_{it} by solving the system,
 - F) checking the convergence of the Newton's method.

Finite strain reformulation of models according to [2] retains the internal structure of a (rate-independent) ‘‘Constitutive Model’’ in (1) and employs the logarithmic (Hencky) strain as the input strain, i.e.

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \ln C. \quad (2)$$

Such a choice is especially beneficial for inelastic models relying on the assumption of additivity of strains, since the additivity is preserved in the logarithmic strain space. However, the stress measure work-conjugate to (2) provided by the model, as well as the tangent modulus, have to be transformed to objects compatible with the formulation of the FEM. Let us consider deformation gradient, F , and the first Piola Kirchhoff (nominal) stress, P , as the conjugate pair for the variational formulation of FEM, and denote the corresponding tangent modulus as \mathbb{M} ; then the transformations $T \rightarrow P$ and $\mathbb{D} \rightarrow \mathbb{M}$ must be applied. The corresponding transformation tensors \mathbb{P} and \mathbb{L} are obtained with the relations (see [2] for details)

$$\mathbb{P} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial F}, \quad \mathbb{L} = \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial F^2}, \quad (3)$$

and the transformation formulae take the forms

$$P = T : \mathbb{P}, \quad \mathbb{M} = \mathbb{P}^T : \mathbb{D} : \mathbb{P} + T : \mathbb{L}. \quad (4)$$

We also recall the following relation for the (symmetric) second Piola-Kirchhoff stress S and the (symmetric) Cauchy stress σ in terms of P

$$S = F^{-1} P, \quad \sigma = \frac{1}{\det F} P F^\top. \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. Reference and computed deformed configurations from the example. The initial state is in green, half tensile stretch in orange, full tensile stretch (five times the initial length) in red, half compression stretch in cyan, and full compression (quarter the initial length) in blue.

3. Example: Uniaxial Stretching of Elastic Cube

Let us illustrate the approach and its incorporation into FEM on an example. For simplicity, let us consider a constitutive model without internal variables or parameters, i.e. $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{P} = \emptyset$. In such a case, the complete computational workflow can be summarized as shown in Box “Algorithm 1” above. Let us note that actions **A–C** must be performed at all integration points.

The workflow is then implemented and validated on a boundary value problem of uniaxial stretching of an elastic cube. The cube is stretched in one direction up to five times its initial length, then returned to its initial length, and finally compressed to one-quarter of its initial length, see Fig. 1. This is imposed by prescribing displacements (a nonhomogeneous Dirichlet boundary condition) on one face of the cube in the direction of loading/unloading, whereas the opposite face remains fixed in that direction. For the constitutive model, we employ a linear isotropic Hooke’s law i.e.

$$\mathbf{T} = \Lambda \text{tr}(\mathbf{E})\mathbf{I} + 2\mu\mathbf{E} \quad (6)$$

with Λ, μ being the Lamé constants. Motivated by [3] and without loss of generality, we set $\Lambda = \mu$. Denoting the stretch ratio parallel and perpendicular to the stretching direction as λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively, one gets: $F_{11} = \lambda_1, F_{22} = F_{33} = \lambda_2, F_{ij} = 0$ for $i, j \in \{1, 2, 3\} \wedge i \neq j$.

Fig. 2. A comparison of analytical and FEM-computed values of component C_{11} and stretch ratio λ_2 as functions of λ_1 for the elastic cube example.

Fig. 3. A comparison of the analytical and FEM-computed values of the non-zero component of current (T_{11}), nominal (P_{11}), 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff (S_{11}), and Cauchy (σ_{11}) stresses as functions of λ_1 for the elastic cube example.

It is then a matter of algebraic manipulations employing relations (2)–(5) to successively derive the following analytical formulas:

$$C_{11} = \lambda_1^2, \quad E_{11} = \ln \lambda_1, \quad \lambda_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt[4]{\lambda_1}},$$

$$\frac{T_{11}}{\mu} = \frac{5}{2} \ln \lambda_1, \quad \frac{P_{11}}{\mu} = \frac{5 \ln \lambda_1}{2 \lambda_1}, \quad \frac{S_{11}}{\mu} = \frac{5 \ln \lambda_1}{2 \lambda_1^2}, \quad \frac{\sigma_{11}}{\mu} = \frac{5 \ln \lambda_1}{2 \sqrt{\lambda_1}}. \quad (7)$$

To verify the numerical implementation, Figs. 2 and 3 compare these analytical formulas with the values computed via in-house FEM. A finite-strain computational analysis of more complex boundary value problems involving large rotations and deflections with a constitutive model featuring a rate-independent inelastic deformation mechanism can be found in [4].

Acknowledgements

This work has been financially supported by the Operational Programme Johannes Amos Comenius of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport of the Czech Republic, within the frame of project Ferroc Multifunctionalities (FerrMion) [project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004591], co-funded by the European Union.

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